

LONG FIBRE WAVINESS PREDICTION BY A 3D FEM CURING MODEL FOR THICK THERMOSETTING EPOXY MATRICES

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SUMMARY

A study for long fibre microbuckling instability in thermosetting resins is presented. The originality stays in the use of a 3D coupling model for the curing of the resin. Fibre waviness observed during the curing was predicted by the model and, by the way, provides a first validation for internal stress prediction in thermosetting matrices.

Keywords: FEM, fibre microbuckling, curing, epoxy matrix, internal stresses

INTRODUCTION

The question of the thermosetting laminate's quality is becoming a new strategic question especially since the increase of structural applications. In behalf of design improvement and costs optimization, a highly accurate knowledge of material properties and of the internal state obtained at the end of the manufacturing process is required. However if the strengthening of the composite is mainly driven by the quality of the fibre reinforcement, it also strongly depends on the quality of the matrix obtained at the end of the curing process and on its interaction with the reinforcement during the curing. It is well known that long fibres are subjected to a waviness phenomenon that appears during the curing of laminates. This denotes internal stresses that are developed during the curing [1, 2] and is therefore especially bad for the structural strengthening of fibre-reinforced composites [3].

It is obvious to understand that fibres undulations are a visible manifestation of internal stresses developed during the curing since they were initially straight. Some authors were convinced that the main mechanism of fibre waviness, and hence corresponding internal stress development, was generated by the cooling step of the curing. However, based on a simple single fibre model, a new approach was proposed in a previous work [1] for the question of fibre microbuckling mechanism. It was demonstrated that chemical shrinkage associated to the curing is the power unit for fibre alignment destabilization, and hence the hypothesis of fibre waviness induced during the cooling stage fails. Fibre can be considered as a beam surrounded by a matrix acting as a foundation that interacts. Polarised light pictures of microbuckling on single fibre specimens clearly established the existence of a matrix area affected by fibre undulation

as shown in Figure 1. Moreover, it was observed that the fibre instability phenomenon is repetitious and that the waviness is periodic.

Figure 1: Carbon fibre microbuckling and description of the matrix area affected by the T300 carbon fibre microbuckling within an LY556 epoxy matrix [1].

In an elastic framework, it was shown that fibre microbuckling instability mechanism can be described by following equation of balance:

$$E_f I_f \frac{d^4 v}{dx^4} + [\pi (R^2 + r^2) r \frac{G_m}{(R-r)} - N] \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} + 2\pi r \frac{E_m}{R} v = 0 \quad (1)$$

R denotes the interacting matrix radius surrounding the fibre whose radius is noted r . E_f denotes fibre longitudinal Young modulus and I_f quadratic moment of the fibre section. G_m and E_m are respectively the shear modulus and Young modulus of the matrix and N is the normal force applied to fibre section. The transverse displacement field solution of equation (1) is searched under a classical sinusoidal form like: $v(x) = A \sin(\alpha x)$ where α denotes the wave number and A the amplitude. The authors showed that this lead to the critical buckle instability load $P(\alpha)$ as a function of wave number as follows:

$$P(\alpha) = -\pi (R^2 + r^2) r \frac{G_m}{(R-r)} + E_f I_f \alpha^2 + \frac{2\pi r E_m}{\alpha^2 R} \quad (2)$$

FEA computation of elastic applied load, consequently to chemical shrinkage during the curing on a T300 carbon fibre in an LY556 epoxy resin, and performed by taking into account a basic matrix's Young modulus evolutions during cure, demonstrated that fibre critical buckle instability load $P(\alpha)$ can be reached during all the thermosetting stage of the resin. This was confirmed later by a detailed real time video record of fibre microbuckling instability that was clearly observed during the chemical reaction stage of the curing [2]. The instability happens quickly in around 10 seconds, is a reproducible and systematic phenomenon and was observed in an epoxy and in a polyester matrix with the same T300 carbon fibre. This experimental observation confirms that fibre waviness is an excellent internal stress indicator and the video confirms that internal stresses are generated during the hot stage of the curing. Knowledge about matrix formation during the curing is the key point of fibre waviness phenomenon.

This study presents therefore the development of a numerical tool, devoted to industrial FEA software like Abaqus®, to provide as easily as possible appropriate information for the description of the curing of a thermosetting resin. For these purposes a constitutive model of an epoxy resin, expressing the couplings that have to be taken into account, is presented in the second part of the paper. Numerical tools developed are presented and

corresponding models for cure kinetics and thermal properties are detailed. The elastic constitutive law of an epoxy matrix during its thermosetting reaction is built from experimental fits of DMA-TMA (Dynamical Mechanical Analysis-Thermal Mechanical Analysis) results. A comparison with experimental data of internal temperature history prediction throughout the curing is discussed in the third part of the paper. An application to internal stress prediction is then proposed in the fourth part of the paper with the study of fibre waviness prediction, in the framework of elasticity.

A 3D THERMAL, CHEMICAL AND MECHANICAL COUPLING MODEL OF THE CURING

Constitutive model

In order to build the model, following assumptions are done:

- Only the elastic mechanical behaviour is considered during the curing time.
- Equation of species diffusion is assumed only controlled by the chemistry and for the case of epoxies with a non linear chemistry as given by the cure kinetics model.
- Species diffusion effects on the mechanics and matrix properties are considered as being second order effects.

In this framework, mechanical balance equation is classically written as follows:

$$\vec{\text{div}} \{ \lambda (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^e}) \underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}} + 2 \mu \underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^e} \} = \vec{\mathbf{0}} \quad (3)$$

where λ and μ are the Lamé coefficients. Notation $(\underline{\underline{\quad}})$ stands for second order tensor. Term $\underline{\underline{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^e}$ denotes the elastic (or instantaneous) strain tensor and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{I}}}$ is the identity tensor. The local temperature T of the matrix during the curing is defined by following equation of heat transfer:

$$\rho C_p \frac{dT}{dt} = \text{div} \{ \lambda_T [\vec{\text{grad}} T] \} + r + \rho \Delta H^r \frac{d\alpha}{dt} - T \{ (3\lambda + 2\mu) \alpha_T \} \text{tr} \underline{\underline{\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^e}} \quad (4)$$

where C_p , λ_T , and r stand respectively for specific heat, thermal conductivity and heat radiation imposed by the oven. α_T is the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the matrix in formation.

Note that the heat flow produced by the chemical reaction, as defined by differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) analysis, is given by term $\rho \Delta H^r \frac{d\alpha}{dt}$, where ΔH^r stands for the enthalpy of the reaction and α stands for the local degree of cure of the reaction. The solving of equation of heat (4) requires information about material parameters such as specific heat, thermal conductivity, degree of cure or CTE that are written in bold characters. Moreover, evolution laws are requested for material parameters since the matrix is a different material at each time of the curing and this point cannot be neglected. In the same way, elastic strain evolution must be defined during the curing. Evolution laws for material parameters, curing characteristics and strain formulation that are highlighted by bold letters in the heat transfer equation were described by the authors in a previous work [4] and are summarized hereafter. However, because of the impossibility to perform material parameters identification tests for any degree of cure, models must be developed for material parameters and strain evolutions dependency to the degree of cure.

Elastic Strain Modeling

The curing of thermosetting systems owns thermal strain and chemical strain (shrinkage). By considering only the elastic approach, and in the framework of small perturbation that is assumed here, the total strain increment component can be expressed as:

$$d\epsilon_{ij}(t) = d\epsilon_{ij}^e(t) + d\epsilon_{ij}^{ch}(t) + d\epsilon_{ij}^{th}(t) \quad (5)$$

where $d\epsilon_{ij}^e(t)$, $d\epsilon_{ij}^{ch}(t)$ and $d\epsilon_{ij}^{th}(t)$ denote respectively the ij component of elastic strain increment, chemical shrinkage strain increment and thermal strain increment.

Chemical Strain Model

The Li et al. [5] model, that defines chemical shrinkage as a bilinear function of degree of cure with a break point at gelation, was adopted here. The fit of the Li et al. model was performed with experimental data provided by the LY556 epoxy resin manufacturer for a 120°C isothermal curing. Break point at gelation was identified at (conversion = 55%; cure shrinkage = -5.5%). The total cure shrinkage of -6% at 100% of degree of cure was extrapolated from the bilinear relationship. The experimental data was provided by the resin manufacturer by help of the Archimedes technique.

Matrix Thermal Strain Estimation during the Curing

Matrix temperature is variable and non uniform during the curing, for heat transfer and exothermal effects reasons. The heterogeneous temperature field generates expansion or shrinkage. An additional difficulty is linked to the fact the curing of the resin is related to a different and changing material at each time. At each time, thermal volume strain evolution for a temperature increment ΔT can be expressed by following linear relation where α_T stands for the CTE of the blend.

$$d\epsilon^{Vol}_{thermal\ ij}(t) = \alpha_T(t) \Delta T \cdot \delta_{ij} \quad (6)$$

One way to solve the determination of the changing CTE is to consider the chemical blend as a mixture of resin and matrix weighted by the degree of cure.

In this context, coefficient $\alpha_T(t)$ is defined by:

$$\alpha_T(t) = [1 - \alpha(t)] \alpha_{T\ uncured\ epoxy} + \alpha(t) \alpha_{T\ fully\ cured\ epoxy}(t) \quad (7)$$

which is a mixture rule relation weighted by the degree of cure, between the uncured liquid state (resin) and the fully cured solid state (matrix). $\alpha_{T\ uncured\ epoxy}$ denotes the thermal expansion coefficient per unit volume for the epoxy resin in its liquid state before gelation and $\alpha_{T\ fully\ cured\ epoxy}$ denotes the thermal expansion coefficient per unit volume for the fully cured epoxy matrix. However, for amorphous polymers, like epoxies, $\alpha_{T\ fully\ cured\ epoxy}$ is temperature dependant and glass transition dependent. Identification of coefficients of thermal expansion for the LY556 epoxy system was performed by DMA-TMA analysis. Thus, for the LY epoxy system, $\alpha_{T\ liquid\ epoxy} = 5E-4$ °C⁻¹ and $\alpha_{T\ fully\ cured\ epoxy} = 450E-6$ °C⁻¹ for a vitrified matrix (below T_g) and $\alpha_{T\ fully\ cured\ epoxy} = 450E-6 + 4.1E-6 (T-T_g)$ for a rubbery matrix (above T_g).

This modelling requires T_g determination at each time of the curing. T_g was calculated by the usual Pascault and Williams [6] relation (also called Di-Benedetto equation) as follows:

$$(T_g - T_{g0}) / (T_{g_{\infty}} - T_{g0}) = \lambda \alpha / [1 - (1 - \lambda) \alpha] \quad (8)$$

with T_{g0} (T_g at $\alpha = 0$) = -37°C and $T_{g_{\infty}} = 136^\circ\text{C}$, for the LY556 epoxy where λ is an adjustable, structure-dependent parameter, and was found equal to 0.57.

Thermal properties evolution during the curing

A proposal for thermal properties description during the curing was presented by the author in a previous paper [4]. Especially, specific heat and conductivity were described as simple as possible for easy FEA programming.

Specific heat ($\text{J/g}^\circ\text{C}$)

In a similar way as for the coefficient of thermal expansion, an easy way for the description of the epoxy matrix specific heat evolution is to consider that it can be described by a linear mixture rule relation, weighted by the degree of cure as follows:

$$C_p(\alpha, T) = (1 - \alpha) C_p(0, T) + \alpha C_p(1, T) \quad (9)$$

where $C_p(0, T)$ and $C_p(1, T)$ stand for liquid resin and fully cured matrix, temperature dependant, specific heat evolutions. Note that a dependence on T_g was introduced for $C_p(1, T)$. Identification of $C_p(0, T)$ and $C_p(1, T)$, by DSC with MDSCTM option, lead to almost linear evolution versus temperature as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} C_p(0, T) &= 1.8500 + 0.002625T \quad (\text{J/g}^\circ\text{C}) \\ C_p(1, T) &= 1.3125 + 0.004437T \quad \text{J/g}^\circ\text{C} \quad \text{for } T < T_{g_{\infty}} \\ C_p(1, T) &= 1.8500 + 0.002625T \quad \text{J/g}^\circ\text{C} \quad \text{for } T \geq T_{g_{\infty}} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$T_{g_{\infty}}$ denotes the glass transition temperature of the fully cured matrix and was found equal to 136°C . Note that a dependence on T_g was introduced for $C_p(1, T)$.

Thermal conductivity ($\text{W/m}^\circ\text{C}$)

In the same way as for specific heat, thermal conductivity is expressed by a linear mixture rule relation weighted by the degree of cure. Thanks to Bailleul et al. [7] and Olofsson [8] works, thermal conductivity was estimated as follows:

$$\lambda(\alpha, T) = (1 - \alpha) \lambda(0) + \alpha \lambda(1, T) \quad (11)$$

$$\lambda(1, T) = -2.727 \cdot 10^{-4} T + 3555.529 \cdot 10^{-4} \quad (\text{W/m}^\circ\text{C}) \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda(0) = 0.180 \quad \text{W/m}^\circ\text{C}$$

$\lambda(0)$ and $\lambda(1, T)$ stand for liquid resin and fully cured matrix, temperature dependant, thermal conductivity evolutions.

Heat flow of the thermosetting reaction (w/m³)

DSC analysis enables the determination of the heat flow of the thermosetting reaction at a given temperature. The heat flow $\phi(t)$ produced by the chemical reaction associated to the curing of a thermosetting resin is a linear function of the rate of degree of cure, with a slope corresponding to the mass enthalpy variation ΔH^f of the reaction such as:

$$\phi(t) = \rho \Delta H^f(T) d\alpha/dt \quad (12)$$

ρ denotes the density. Density variation during the curing was not taken into account here since its variation is very small and was fixed at $\rho=1170.6\text{Kg/m}^3$ for the LY556 epoxy blend studied in this paper. ΔH^f temperature dependency during the cure corresponds to enthalpy temperature dependency that was indentified by several isothermal DSC scans. This technique enables determination of the total (ultimate) heat of the reaction (H_U) generated during dynamic scanning. Thus, enthalpy measured for isothermal curing (H_T) could be compared with the ultimate heat of the reaction (H_U) as defined by:

$$\frac{H_T}{H_U} = \begin{cases} 0.00243T - 0.16003 & T < 473 \text{ }^\circ\text{K} \\ 1 & T \geq 473 \text{ }^\circ\text{K} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Thus, ΔH^f was considered as following a linear evolution that ends at the ultimate value H_U of $355 \pm 25 \text{ J/g}$, in agreement with the literature for the same epoxy resin system.

Cure Kinetics Model

Cure kinetics for the case of epoxies is well known in the literature. Many works established a non linear expression governing the rate of degree of conversion. It is usually a power law whose coefficients are modulated by the temperature and for epoxies the Kamal and Souror model [9] was widely used. However, diffusion effects exist for epoxies and Fournier et al. [10] proposed a semi-empirical relationship (14) based on free volume consideration to extend the Kamal and Sourour model by a diffusion factor $f_d(\alpha)$ such as:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = [a_1 \exp(-e_1/T) + a_2 \exp(-e_2/T) \alpha^m] (1-\alpha)^n f_d(\alpha), \quad (14)$$

$$\text{with } f_d(\alpha) = \left[\frac{2}{(1 + \exp[(\alpha - \alpha_f)/b])} - 1 \right]$$

α_f is the degree of conversion obtained at the end of a given isothermal curing and hence could be directly obtained as the ratio between H_T and H_U for each isothermal DSC scans. b is an empirical diffusion factor of the material.

These parameters are listed in Table 1 for the LY556 epoxy blend (HY917 hardener and QY070 accelerator, mass ratio: 100:90:2).

Table 1: Cure kinetics coefficients of the LY556 epoxy resin system for the Kamal and Sourour model.

m	n	$A_1 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	$A_2 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	$E_1 \text{ (J/mol)}$	$E_2 \text{ (J/mol)}$
1	2	1339879.1750	21042820.6887	69141.4796	72620.17984

The other parameters, such as diffusion factor b and final degree of conversion α_f , were found to vary linearly with the temperature, and are defined by: $b = 7.1588E-04 T(^{\circ}K) - 2.2816E-01$ and $\alpha_f = 4.0646E-03 T(^{\circ}K) - 8.2434E-01$.

Mechanical Behavior Description

Mechanical behaviour of the resin during the curing was performed by DMA-TMA tests. Since the resin was initially liquid, only shear tests were possible to carry out its behaviour during the curing. Shear test results were first obtained as a function of time during a 120°C isothermal curing. These results were then plotted as a function of degree of cure thanks to the degree of cure evolution during the curing as given by DSC scans or by cure kinetics model.

The description of shear modulus as a function of the degree of cure only is critical since it is well known that it depends also of the temperature [11]. However, the aim here is to check the possibilities of the coupling model approach for a given cure to simulate. Further extension of this approach for any cure must contain temperature dependency. As experimental data for elastic behaviour were accurately reachable by shear tests for liquid resin at the beginning of the curing, it appears to be more appropriate to express the elastic constitutive law as a function of shear modulus G' and bulk modulus K , with a dependency to the degree of conversion α as following, where t denotes the curing time:

$$\sigma_{ij}(t) = [K(\alpha) - \frac{2}{3} G'(\alpha)] \text{tr}(\epsilon^e(t)) \cdot \delta_{ij} + 2G'(\alpha) \epsilon_{ij}^e(t) \quad (15)$$

Thus, in this context, bulk modulus evolution versus degree of cure $K(\alpha)$ was estimated by a mixture rule relation between 3 GPa. for the liquid state and 6.3 GPa. for the solid state [12] as given by:

$$K(\alpha) = (1-\alpha) K(0) + \alpha K(1) \quad (16)$$

Where $K(0)$ and $K(1)$ stand for uncured resin state and fully cured resin state respectively.

THE FEA MODELLING

Precise details about moduli evolutions versus conversion and about the numerical solving strategy were presented by the author in a previous work [4]. This solving strategy was applied to a cylindrical block of resin (diameter 32 mm, height 30 mm) poured in a steel tube with a thickness of 6mm. The heating of the steel tube containing the liquid resin was reproduced by the FEM analysis. A special attention was given to the determination of the convection interaction determination between the steel test tube and the air of the oven in order to reproduce as realistic as possible real conditions of oven heating that corresponds to a 3°C/min ramp followed by a 100°C plateau. Due to the axial symmetry of the structure the mesh was performed with 8-node thermally coupled axisymmetric solid, biquadratic displacement, bilinear temperature CAX8T elements of the Abaqus® element library. The full model requires 240 elements and 787 nodes for results convergence. The computation time takes around 25 min. on a Pentium IV HT desktop at 3.20 GHz with 2Go of Ram.

Local temperature and degree of cure gradient predictions

As displayed in Fig. 2, three thermocouple probes were put inside of the epoxy resin to record internal temperature evolutions. Points 1, 2 and 3 stand respectively for the centre of the block, the lateral edge of the block at the middle of its height, and at the bottom of the block. Comparisons between internal temperature measurements and prediction given by the model for the epoxy resin curing are presented in Fig. 2. Internal temperature prediction (full lines) almost fit experimental data recorded during the curing, and especially amplitude and appearance of the exothermic behaviour of the curing were predicted in a very satisfying way by the model.

The solving of the thermal and chemical coupling model enables, simultaneously to local temperature prediction, prediction for corresponding local degree of cure as given by equation (14). As degree of cure accounts for matrix formation, gradients of curing will necessarily lead to gradients of matrix state and hence properties gradients within the epoxy block. This is one of the basic mechanisms for internal stress developments. Thermal and curing gradients as displayed in Figure 2 and in Figure 3 must therefore be considered for further cure optimization strategy.

Figure 2: Comparison between local temperatures predicted by the model and from measurements in a 30 mm thick epoxy (LY556 epoxy resin, ramp 3°C/min and 100°C plateau).

Figure 3: Degree of cure gradients predicted within a 7.5mm thick epoxy matrix during the 3°C/min ramp and 100°C plateau.

Discussion

Results provided by the three dimensional curing model, coupled with the heat generated by the thermosetting reaction, lead to very satisfying results concerning local internal temperature prediction that fits well with the experiment. It seems reasonable to consider this as a first validation of the coupling model. Corresponding local degree of cure was predicted by the solving of the cure kinetics equation. Thus, as a consequence, the mechanics of the matrix in formation could be computed since it was introduced in the model as a function of degree of cure. Nevertheless, the quality of the coupling model with the mechanics (elasticity) was assessed with the fibre waviness simulation. This point is presented in next section of this paper for fibre waviness prediction.

FIRST FIBRE WAVINESS APPEARANCE PREDICTION

Fibre waviness prediction requires the corresponding compressive stress induced by the curing to trigger microbuckling instability. The matrix surrounding the fibre must be not able to avoid the buckling instability. Fibre critical load instability will depend on the ratio between matrix modulus and fibre modulus (equation 2). The compressive destabilizing load generated by the curing is thus in competition with the critical load. An inaccurate cure modelling will then fails for fibre microbuckling simulation.

The Single Fibre Specimen Curing

The curing model is applied on a single T300 carbon fibre embedded by a LY556 epoxy resin. A two dimensional meshing with 8-nodes biquadratic displacement, bilinear temperature, plane strain element (CPE8T) was used for the Abaqus FEM simulation. A rectangular matrix shape of 10 mm of length and a width of 7mm with a thickness of fibre diameter (7 microns) was meshed. A 8mm long carbon fibre was meshed with the same elements and was located 1.75mm below the top of the matrix accordingly to fibre microbuckling curing conditions [2]. The single fibre specimen geometry is displayed in Figure 4. This sample was heated with temperature boundary condition applied along its width on the lower face and corresponds to a heating with a ramp of around 5°C/min followed by a plateau at 138°C.

Fibre Waviness Results

Fibre waviness was predicted by the simulation during the hot stage of the curing. The wavelength obtained at the end of the plateau stabilizes around 2mm and the amplitude around 7 microns. Fibre waviness predicted is shown in Figure 5. The results are very encouraging and are coherent with the physics of the matrix surrounding the fibre. The matrix is logically into a tensile stress state induced by the chemical shrinkage on one hand and, on the other hand, by the fibre that tries to dilate.

Figure 4: Finite element mesh of the half single fibre specimen.

Figure 5: T300 carbon fibre waviness prediction (deformation scale factor : 5).

CONCLUSION

The simulation of the curing of a single fibre specimen with microbuckling curing conditions [2], despite that it was done with a 2D meshing, leads to successful results.

Even if results for fibre wavelength obtained here of around 2 mm are far from those observed with the real experiment (around 115 microns before cooling for a 10 mm diameter cylindrical matrix), it is important to remark that the simulation done here corresponds to a thin plate of matrix since the thickness was fibre diameter. One may compare simulation results with thin laminates fibre waviness measurement developed by Paluch [13], which has rebuilt the three-dimensional progress of T300 carbon fibres inside of an epoxy 914 matrix ply, using fibres cross section cuttings and an appropriate statistical analysis of the position of fibres section centres. Paluch observed waviness to be around 1200 to 2400 microns with amplitude between 0.5 and 6 microns. From this point of view results seem to be satisfying. However, this kind of comparison can only be qualitative since, even if small thickness of matrix were studied in both cases, one cannot make direct comparison between single fibre results and laminate results, namely for fibre neighbouring interactions in the laminate. Moreover, the simulation was only performed during the curing and the cooling stage was not studied. This point need material improvement during the cooling for the model and, due to the thermal mismatch between fibre and matrix, fibre wavelength might certainly be decreased. Anyway, fibre waviness was predicted in elasticity by the simulation and hence validates the model presented in this paper. Further material description should be provided, namely for viscoelasticity, T_g crossing and for the cooling. This should enable quantitative residual stress level and fine fibre microbuckling predictions.

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